

BODY PARTS IDENTIFIED WITH RASI/ZODIAC, PLANETS AND DISEASES CAUSED BY THEM

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Cite This Article: Sankar S & Dr. V. Kotravel, “Body Parts Identified with Rasi/Zodiac, Planets and Diseases Caused by Them”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 18-21, 2023.

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Abstract:

In this article we will analyze the links between Rasi & body parts and planets and diseases caused by them. Medical astrology is gaining strength currently and many are considering views from an astrologer before going for any major medical treatment or surgery. An astrologer is in a position to handle such expectations because of many earlier texts on astrology talks about the connections between Rasi/Zodiac and the body parts. Also, the link between planets and diseases or planets and body parts. So, we will analyze few such old and next texts on medical astrology to establish that this link exists.

Key Words: Sun, Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, Saturn, Rahu, Ketu, House or Bhava, Ascendant or Lagna, Rasi, Mesham(Aries), Rishabam(Taurus), Mithunam(Gemini), Katakam(Cancer), Simham(Leo), Kanni (Virgo), Thulam (Libra), Vrichigam (Scorpio), Dhanushu (Sagittarius), Makaram (Capricorn), Kumbham (Aquarius), Meenam (Pisces), Drekkana (D-3 chart), Dasa, Buddhi

Introduction:

We will discuss about the body parts indicated by Zodiac or Rasi & the link between Planets and diseases caused by them for an individual. We will see this from the perspective of D-1 charts and D-3 chart. Drekkana chart (D-3) uses different logic to identify the body parts. We will refer the various old texts as well as new texts for this purpose. We are including points from present day astrologers as they cover the current trend in diseases and complications in health.

Analysis:

In Mantreswara’s Phaladeepika, 4th sloka in 1st Chapter explains the body parts identified to 12 houses. “Assuming that the horoscope represents the Kalapurusha, then the parts of the body beginning with the Ascendant (Lagna) will be as under:”

- First house (Lagna-Ascendant) — the head
- Second house — the face
- Third house — the breast
- Fourth house — the heart
- Fifth house — the belly
- Sixth house — the waist
- Seventh house — the groins
- Eighth house — the private parts (Sexual organs)
- Ninth house — the two thighs
- Tenth house — the two knees
- Eleventh house — the two calves
- Twelfth house — the two feet

பாதங்கள் Feet	தலை Head	முகம் Face	புஜங்கள் Arms
கணுக்கால்கள் Ankles	மேஷ லக்னம் ARIES Ascendant (கால புருஷத் தத்துவம் / Natural Zodiac)		இதயம் Heart
மூட்டுகள் Knees			வயிறு Stomach
தொடைகள் Thighs	இனப்பெருக்க உறுப்புகள் Reproductive organs	அடிவயிறு Space below Naval	இடுப்பு Hip

Notes: The house which is occupied or aspected by benefits or whose lord is bestowed with strength, the part of the body represented by that house will be strong and well built. If the lord of a house be weak or be occupied or otherwise afflicted by a malefic, the corresponding part of the body will be weak or diseased. We can present the above in a diagram as given below for easy reference.

The present-day astrologers further extended the body parts to a large extent covering all major body parts. Given below is one such classification of body parts by Zodiac/House

Pisces or 12th House Feet, Left Eye	Aries or Lagna Head, Brain, Mind	Tarua or 2nd House Face, Eyes, Nose, Tongue, Teeth, Ears, Fingers, Nails, Bones, flesh	Gemini or 3rd House Neck, Throat, Collar bones, hands, breathing, body growth
Aquarius or 11th House Buttocks and Breathing, Legs in general, Left ear	Mesha Lagnam / Kalapurusha Tathuvam		Cancer or 4th House Heart, Lungs, Chest, Breast, blood
Capricorn or 10th House Knees, Bones and flesh, Patella, Popliteal Fossae			Leo or 5th House Upper Abdomen, Mind, Heart, Liver, Gall bladder, Spleen, Intestines, Mesentery
Sagittarius or 9th House Thighs anemorl Arteries	Scorpio- or 8th House External Genitals, Urine, Blood, Seminal Vessels	Libra or 7th House Groins, Semen, Female Organs, Breathing, Bladder, Uterus, Ovaries, Prostate Glands, Pineal Gland	Virgo or 6th House Lower Abdomen, Navel, Flesh, Mnetal faculties, Anus, Kidneys

There is another classification of body parts based on Drekkana (D-3 chart). A zodiac or rasi is split into three equal parts with 10 degrees and a planet posited in the first Drekkana (1 – 10 degrees) is placed in the same zodiac or rasi in D-3 chart, planet posited in the 2nd drekkana (10 to 20 degrees) is placed in the 5th house from that zodiac or rasi in D-3 chart and a planet posited in the 3rd drekkana(20 to 30 degrees) will be placed in the 9th house from that zodiac or rasi in D-3 chart. Based on drekkana, the body parts are classified as given below.

12 Cusps	1st Drekkna	2nd Drekkna	3rd Drekkna
Frist Cusp	Head	Neck	Pelvis
Second Cusp	Right Eye	Right Shoulder	Generating Organ
Third Cusp	Right Ear	Right Arm	Right Testicle
Fourth Cusp	Right Nostril	Right side of body	Right Thigh
Fifth Cusp	Right Check	Right auricle & Ventricle of Heart	Right Knee
Sixth Cusp	Right Jaw	Right Lung	Right Calf
Seventh Cusp	Mouth	Naval	Legs
Eighth Cusp	Left Jaw	Left Lung	Left Calf
Nineth Cusp	Left Check	Left auricle & Ventricle of Heart	Left Knee
Tenth Cusp	Left Nostril	Left side of body	Left Thigh
Eleventh Cusp	Left Ear	Left Arm	Left Testicle
Twelfth Cusp	Let Eye	Left Shoulder	Anus

We have seen above how the rasi/zodiac is identified to a body parts and that will help one to understand the likely parts of body to be affected based on their birth chart and planet transitions. Now we will see the connection between planets and diseases and what kind of diseases a planet can cause to an individual.

In Phaladeepika, it is also stated that the diseases caused by different planets.

- All matters relating to diseases should be ascertained from (a) the planets in the 6th house, (b) the planets in the 8th house (c) the planets in the 12th house, (d) the lord of the 6th house and (e) the planets associated with the lord of the 6th house. The particular disease may be predicted if the same happens to be indicated by two, three or more independent planetary dispositions.
- The Sun is the significator for following diseases and troubles (1) bile, (2) high fever, (3) burning in the body, (4) epilepsy, (5) heart diseases, (6) eye troubles (7) stomach troubles, (8) skin diseases (9) leukorrhoea, (10) danger from enemies, (11) danger from wood, fire, weapon and poison, (12) distress from wife and sons, (13) danger from thieves or quadrupeds, (14) danger from snakes (15) danger from the king, the God Yama and God Shiva.
- The Moon's significations in this chapter are (1) Excessive sleepiness or sleeplessness, (2) laziness, (3) phlegmatic affliction, (4) dysentery or diarrhea, (5) carbuncle, (6) typhoid fever, (7) danger from

horned or watery animals or creatures, (8) loss of appetite, (9) indigestion (10) tastelessness, (11) trouble from women (12) jaundice, (13) impurity of blood, (14) danger from water, (15) mental fatigue (16) fear from Balagrahas, the Goddess Durga, kinnaras, the God yama, snakes, and female Yaksha.

- Mars can be the cause of following diseases and troubles (1) Excessive thirst, (2) morbid irritation due to billious fever, (3) fear or danger from fire, poison or weapon, (4) leprosy, (5) eye troubles, (6) appendicitis, (7) epilepsy, (8) injury to the marrow, (9) itch in the body, (10) roughness of the body, (11) bodily deformities, (12) fear from the king, fire and thieves, (13) quarrels with brothers, sons or enemies, (14) fighting with the enemies, (15) diseases in the upper part of the body and (16) fear from evil spirits, gandharva and frightful demon.
- Mercury is concerned with the following diseases and troubles (1) mental confusion (2) harsh speech or trouble in vocal organs, (3) eye troubles, (4) diseases of the throat, (5) trouble in the nose or nasal affliction, (6) fever caused by imbalance of the three humours - wind, bile and phlegm, (7) ill effects from poisoning (like food poisoning), (8) skin diseases, (9) jaundice, (10) itching and bad dreams, (11) fear from fire. (12) hard labour, (13) diseases or evil caused by gandharvas etc.
- Jupiter is responsible for the following diseases and troubles (1) Appendicitis, (2) fever due to infection in intestines, (3) fainting, (4) diseases of the ear, (5) troubles in connection with temple matters, (6) Distress due to curse of Brahmin (7) troubles due to hoarded wealth, (8) oppression caused by Vidyadhara, Yaksha, kinnaras, Gods, Serpents etc. (9) Punishment due to show of disrespect to preceptor, respected and elderly persona and deviation from duty towards them. This is suffered during the Antar Dasa of Jupiter. This is so determined by the Divine.
- The diseases and troubles caused by Venus are as follows-(1) Pale complexion due to Anemia, (2) Eye troubles, urinary obstruction, diabetes, diseases of the generative organs due to imbalance of phlegm and wind, (4) lack of vitality, (5) inability to have sexual inter course (impotency), (6) Pale complexion, lack of luster and weakness due to excessive indulgence in sexual intercourse, (7) rickets, (8) fear from witches, female ghosts and female deities (9) break in friendship with dear friends.
- Saturn is likely to be the cause of the following diseases and troubles (1) diseases caused by wind and phlegm, (2) Pain in the legs or becoming lame, (3) fatigue due to excessive labour, (4) mental aberration, (5) Stomachache, (6) Excessive heat in the body, (7) troubles from servants, (8) distress due to wife and children, (9) injury to some part of the body, (10) mental anguish (11) oppression by ignominious goblin and the like, (12) injury from a blow from a piece of wood or stone (13) misfortune.
- The diseases and troubles attributed to Rahu are as follows : (1) Heart diseases, (2) threat of burning, (3) leprosy, (4) aberration of mind, (4) diseases caused by poisoning, (5) pain in the legs or injury, (6) distress from wife and children or distress caused on their account, (7) trouble from goblins, serpents or enemies.
- Ketu is the cause of (1) Trouble through dispute with Brahmins and Kshatriyas.
- The troubles due to Gulik are (1) fear from seeing dead bodies (2) poison, (3) bodily pain, (4) sorrow due to the death of a near relation, (5) fear from evil Spirits". In current time astrologers classified the diseases according to the planets which covers the diseases of present time. We can see such classification by present-day astrologers Durai K Rajagopal, Raj Kumar & Tirukkivilur K B Hariprasath Sarma in their book on Medical Astrology. They are as given below.

Sun: Head, brain related diseases, Heart diseases, Eye problems, bilious diseases, fevers, fits, bone fractures, back pain, Spinal cord issues, jaundice, typhoid, leprosy etc.,

Moon: Mental related disorders, diseases of infancy, lungs, breast cancer, female genitals related, water borne diseases, gastric, dropsy, asthma, bronchitis, Common cold & cough etc.,

Mars: Blood related diseases, female organs, urinary diseases, muscles problem, tumours, cuts, wounds, surgery, burns, small pox, ulcers, fractures, piles, hemorrhage etc.,

Mercury: Nerves related, diseases of brain, speech problems, mouth, ENT issues, leprosy, paralysis, fits, impotency, epilepsy, chicken pox, giddiness, falling from heights etc.,

Jupiter: Obesity, diseases of Kapha, loss of memory, diabetes, insomnia, abscesses, indigestion, gastric troubles, enlargement of organs, tumors, anemia etc.,

Venus: Sexually transmitted diseases, neck pain, sugar problem, bad breath, urinal infections, boils, throat issues, diseases in private parts etc.,,

Saturn: Skin related problems, knee pain, tooth ache, bone marrow issues, deaf, Chronic diseases, muscle stiffness etc.,

Rahu: Addiction of various kinds including drug addiction, infectious diseases, depression problems, hysteria, allergy, digestive problems, stomach ache, gastric problems etc.

Ketu: Reduction in immunity, cancer, unidentified diseases, cataract, mind confusion etc.,

Conclusion:

We have seen how a rasi or zodiac is linked to different body parts and link between planets and diseases it can cause. With these basic concepts, we can look into the position of different planets, rasi's and bhava's, their dasa/budhi periods in an individual's birth chart and combine that with current planet transitions/positions and predict the likely diseases that person might get affected and the likely period of impact. This also helps to identify a person's likely diseases he may get, or likely body parts may get affected and take prevention steps on his life style or food habits to avoid or reduce the impacts.

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